

RESIST / ANCE

strategies for a better world

Game Rules

RESIST/ANCE

strategies for a better world

RESIST/ANCE

Title: RESIST/ANCE—Strategies for a Better World

Produced: 2026

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Based on the RESIST Research Project: www.theresistproject.eu

An output of the RESIST Research Project, ID:101060749

**Funded by
the European Union**

From late 2022 to the end of 2023, the RESIST Research Team mapped how 'anti-gender' politics are produced and expressed in contemporary Europe. The team analysed hundreds of parliamentary debates and thousands of media articles in four case studies focusing on the UK, Poland, Switzerland, and Hungary between 2016 and 2022. They also used controversy mapping techniques to examine intensive outbursts of 'anti-gender' politics in these countries. RESIST findings reveal how 'anti-gender' politics is creating a dynamic political landscape characterised by increasingly hardened ideological positions, political opportunism and a restless search for new targets of discrimination.

In 2024 the RESIST Research Team worked to create new understandings of the effects of 'anti-gender' politics on everyday lives and forms of resistance, using data gathered via interviews, focus groups and a survey across nine case studies: Belarus, people living in exile in Europe, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Poland, Spain (Catalonia & Basque Country) and Switzerland.

The prompts on the cards in this pack are derived from generalised data fragments from the RESIST Research.

The RESIST Zenodo Repository
<https://zenodo.org/communities/resistproject/>

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RESIST/ANCE

strategies for a better world

Welcome to RESIST/ANCE, an empowering, mission-driven, strategic, **collaborative game**, where you can develop strategies to fight oppression, inequalities and injustice. We are delighted that you have a copy of this game, and hope that you find it engaging.

This is a game of interactive play, aimed at developing capacity together to counter 'anti-gender' mobilisations, or **Challenges**. This game helps us do this by exploring how such mobilisations operate, the real-world impacts they have, and **Strategies** to resist them in a space where you can reflect, learn, and act together. The goal is to create collective long-term **Resilience** to build better worlds.

It is intended that this game might facilitate discussion and foster new understandings. To aid in this, you will find team **discussion prompts** in *italics* along the way, prompting engagement with the content of the cards, indicated also by this Chat Icon...

RESIST/ANCE is an output of the RESIST Research Project, which sought to counter 'anti-gender' mobilisations. RESIST used 'anti-gender' mobilisations to describe organised opposition to recent social progress in gender equality, reproductive rights, and the rights and representation of LGBTIQ+ people.

This game is available for free as a .pdf download on the RESIST Zenodo Repository, and the RESIST Website; you can download it, print it, and play it! Alternatively, you can get in touch with the project coordinator Prof. Kath Browne at kath.browne@ucd.ie to request a physical copy be posted to you, while stocks last.

For the full set of RESIST/ANCE resources, scan this QR code...
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>

Visit us at the RESIST Website. We'd love to have you...
www.theresistproject.eu

Objective

In the game RESIST/ANCE, you and your team are people who are challenged on a daily basis by 'anti-gender' mobilisations and their impacts. You have **Strategies** that you have honed, sure, but there are also unexpected **Events** along the way, which in turn have **Effects** that may disrupt, distract, or even sometimes help you, altering how you decide to manage those **Challenges**.

This is a **collaborative** adventure, with no winners or losers, rather an opportunity to sit together to build **Resilience**.

The game ends when you overcome the dealt Challenges using a combination of your available Strategies, earning, losing and spending **Resilience Points (RPs)** along the way.

Players

This game works best with **two or three players**, but can be played by a larger group with a suggested maximum of five players; it is also intended to be suitable for a facilitated workshop of participants in groups of three to five players, with a copy of the game per group. In this case it is recommended that the facilitator understands the rules and is in a position to answer any questions that participants may have.

Playing Time

Once you understand the rules, you can expect this game to take approximately 30 minutes to play with two to three players.

Resources

You can download a .zip file of the full set of RESIST/ANCE resources from the RESIST Zenodo Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>, or via this QR Code, containing the following documents:

RESIST/ANCE Rules Booklet
RESIST/ANCE Resilience Tracker printable
RESIST/ANCE Additional Wild Cards printable
RESIST/ANCE PnP Game (Print and Play)

RESIST/ANCE Card Decks: Challenge & Event...

Fig.1

15 **Challenge Cards**, showing the **green** Challenge Icon in the lower section of the back of each card, and the green **Challenge Strength* Icon** on the top left hand corner of the front of the card.

 (*See note Pg.21)

Over the course of the game, you will face a sequence of Challenges collaboratively at the Challenge Horizon.

40 **Event Cards**, showing the **blue** Event Icon ⚡ in the lower section of the back of each card, and on the top left hand corner of the front of the card.

Each Event Card has an **Effect** ✨ on the lower half of the front of the card that you have to carry out.

You will reveal one Event Card during **Stage 1: What Now!?**, bringing an element of the unexpected which may impact your strategic planning.

RESIST/ANCE Card decks: Strategy & Wild...

Fig.2

46 **Strategy Cards** (including 10 **Synergy Cards**), showing the **orange** Strategy Icon in the lower section of the back of each card.

On the top left hand corner of the front of the card you will also find the card's **Strategy Strength**, and **Synergy Symbol (&)**

You will review Strategy Cards during **Stage 2: Strategise**, and then play them on Challenge Cards during **Stage 3: Act** and **Stage 3: Synergise** to overcome those Challenges.

15 **Wild Cards**, showing the customisable **grey** Wild Icon in the lower section of the back of each card, along with the Strategy and Challenge Icons indicating it can be customised to be either one. The front of the cards also show the grey Wild Icon in the top left, and a customisable Strategy/Challenge header.

You can **customise** the game by creating your own Strategy and Challenge Cards.
(See Pg. 26)

Quick Start

Welcome to the Quick Start for RESIST/ANCE, an empowering **cooperative** Strategy game. Your team is tasked with overcoming four Challenges before running out of Strategies, pitting your Strategy Strengths .

Objective: Work together to overcome all face-up Challenges along the way.

The **game ends** when:

- You overcome all Challenges OR
- You cannot reasonably play or refill Strategies

You will find summary Quick Setup and Quick Rules Reference Cards in your card pack. **Deal one of each to each player.**

Quick Setup (Fig.3)

1. Lay out 15 Strategy Cards face up in a 5x3 grid (**Strategy Toolkit**)
2. Place 5 Strategy Cards face up below it (**Defence Tableau**)
3. Place remaining Strategy Cards face down (**Strategy Deck**)

Quick Rules

1. Lay out 4 Challenge Cards above the Strategy Toolkit (**Challenge Horizon**): 2 face up and 2 face down
2. Place remaining Challenge Cards face down to the left of the Challenge Horizon (**Challenge Deck**)
3. Shuffle Event Cards into a Deck and place to the right of the Strategy Toolkit (**Event Deck**)
4. You will start with 5 RPs printed on your **Resilience Tracker**

Each round has four stages: (1) What Now!?, (2) Strategise, (3) Act, Synergise & Reflect, and (4) Rebalance

Stage 1, What Now!? Draw Event: Flip the top Event Card

Stage 2, Strategise. Discuss which Strategies in your Defence Tableau could tackle the visible Challenges. Review Strategies in your Strategy Toolkit for later rounds.

Stage 3, Act, Synergise & Reflect. For each visible Challenge :

- Play up to 1 Strategy Card from your Defence Tableau onto it
- Add total of played Strategy Strengths together, per Challenge Card
- If total Strategy Strength played on a Challenge Card \geq Challenge Strength \rightarrow Challenge is overcome

Synergise. Score Strategy Strength bonuses if you have played:

- A Synergy Card Strategy Strength
- A Synergy Card

Reflection Bonus

You can earn bonus Resilience Points for pausing to reflect on the Strategies used in this round: can you name specific Actions for each Strategy Card played in this round that you could potentially implement in your own context? One RP is earned for each Action identified; take a note of them on your Resilience Tracker to take away with you from this experience.

Stage 4, Rebalance

- Gain RPs
- Flip one hidden Challenge Card face up, if there are any
- Refill Defence Tableau back to 5 cards from the Strategy Toolkit
- Optionally, spend -2 RPs to refill the Strategy Toolkit from the Strategy Deck

The **game ends**, when:

- All Challenges are overcome OR
- You cannot refill your Defence Tableau

Finally, count your RPs , compare your score to the Team Resilience Chart, and reflect together on what just happened

RESIST/ANCE: Rules of Play in Detail

Components

In this game there are 101 playing **Cards**, all of which show prompts derived from the data gathered by the RESIST Project:

- 15 Challenge Cards
- 40 Event Cards
- 46 Strategy Cards
- of which 10 are Synergy Cards

In addition, there are
 20 Wild Cards which you can customise as Strategy or Challenge Cards

 15 (5 sets of three) double-sided Information Cards, **a set of each of which can be dealt to each player at Setup:** (1) a Quick Setup Card, (2) a Quick Rules Card and (3) a handy QR Codes Card

You Will Also Need:

A **Resilience Tracker Sheet** printable, which you can download from the RESIST Zenodo Repository. This will help you to keep track of progress in the game, via **Resilience Points (RPs)**, but also your own reflections. Print one Resilience Tracker Sheet for the team, or have one per player for **personal takeaways, reflection notes and follow up Actions**—it's up to you! Download via this QR code...
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>

TOP TIP: If you don't have a die or a die app, you can still play this game

Rules of play (this document). You may have a physical copy, but if not, you can read these online, or print them out. These resources are available via the QR code above.

Die A physical die, a die app on your phone, or Google dice roller. A die is used for some decision making in the game. If you don't have a die, have someone pick a random number between 1 and 6 when required.

Pen You can use a pen to customise the cards and to fill in your Resilience Tracker.

Printer If you are printing this yourself as a Print and Play (PnP) game, you will need access to a printer. Fear not: we have designed the cards not only using colour, but also with symbols to indicate Card Type, meaning you can print in black and white if that is what is available to you. You will find printing instructions via the QR Code.

Initial Setup

Gather your components (Fig.4)

Customise the game to your context. As you play, you can discuss the prompts on the cards, customise them for your context, and create new Challenge and Strategy Cards.

Deal the cards (Fig.5). Cards are laid out on a flat playing surface so that all players can see them. You do not hold cards in your hand as in a standard card game.

TOP TIP: You can discover how to customise this game in the 'Customising the RESIST/ANCE Game' section on Pg.26

1. Shuffle the Strategy Cards and deal them out face up in a grid of 5x3. This is your collection of honed Strategies—your **Strategy Toolkit**.
2. Deal five Strategy Cards face up in a row below the Strategy Toolkit. This is your **Defence Tableau**. Your Defence Tableau forms the basis of your defensive Strategy against the Challenge Horizon.
3. Place the remaining Strategy Cards face down in a pile to the left of the Strategy Toolkit. This is your **Strategy Deck**.
4. Shuffle the Challenge Cards , then deal four in a row above the Strategy Toolkit, two face up and two face down. This is your **Challenge Horizon**. Challenges are by nature unpredictable, so you can only see the first two for now.
5. Place the remaining Challenge Cards face down in a pile to the left of the Challenge Horizon. This is your **Challenge Deck**.
6. Shuffle the Event Cards

How to Play

In each round, you will **move through four stages: What Now!?, Strategise, Act, Synergise and Reflect; and Rebalance**. You will continue to play rounds **until Game End is triggered**.

Refer to the 'Key Terms' section on Pg.23 if you would like more detail on the concepts described here. Refer to the 'Check for Game End' section on Pg.18 to read about identifying when the game is over.

You will find team discussion prompts in italics. They are also indicated by this discussion Icon to make them easy to find.

Stage 1: What Now!? Draw an Event Card

(a) Flip over one Event Card ⚡ from the top of the Event Card Deck and place it face up below the Event Card Deck on the Event Card Discard Pile. It will reveal an Event that has just taken place. In the blue box on the lower half of the card, you will find details of the Effect ⚡ that this Event has had.

(b) Consider the Event Prompt, and carry out the Effect described on the lower half of that Event Card.

Discussion prompt: Have you been affected by events such as this? Have they proven to have had a positive or negative effect? Why, and in what way?

(c) An example of an Event Card is shown in **Fig.6**, and again in the context of the full game layout in **Fig.11**.

In this example, the Effect Instructions shown in the blue box on the lower half of the Event Card indicate that the result of the Event is to put one of your usual Strategies out of reach. Further, it outlines that you must discard a Strategy Card from your Defence Tableau at random, outlining the steps to do this, i.e.

(Fig.7) you roll a three and therefore count three cards from the left hand side of your Defence Tableau; discard the card you land on by removing it from your Defence Tableau and placing it on the Strategy Discard Pile.

Fig.7

Discussion prompt: What strategies have you depended on before that are no longer relevant in your context? What changed?

Stage 2: Strategise

Discuss the Strategy Cards currently available to you in your Defence Tableau, and also those in the Strategy Toolkit which you may wish to move to the Defence Tableau in time, as to how they may, or may not, relate to the visible Challenges at the Challenge Horizon; identify which Strategy Cards you plan to play from the Defence Tableau in this round during the Stage 3: Act and Synergise steps.

Discussion prompt: Consider customising the lower half of the Strategy Cards to your own context.

Stage 3: Act, Synergise & Reflect

Act. Tackle the visible Challenges at the **Challenge Horizon** by playing **Strategy Cards** on them. A Challenge Card is overcome once the combined Strength of Strategy Cards played on it is equal to or exceeds the Strength* of that Challenge Card. Complete all Challenges, and the game is over. (*See note Pg.21)

You can **play one Strategy Card from your Defence Tableau per round to each one of the visible Challenges.**

Synergise. The cards you play in Stage 3 can be **Strategy Cards** or those special Strategy Cards called **Synergy Cards** ; Synergy Cards show an '&' **Synergy Symbol** on their Card Type Label. Playing a Synergy Card onto a Strategy or Synergy card earns bonus Strategy Strength. Remember, you cannot play directly from the Strategy Toolkit or the Strategy Deck: only from the Defence Tableau.

Reflect. Earn bonus Resilience Points for pausing to reflect on the Strategies used in this round. Can you name specific Actions for each Strategy Card played in this round that you could potentially implement in your own context? One Resilience Point is earned for each Action identified; take note of them on your Resilience Tracker to take away with you from this experience.

Discussion prompt: Are any challenges you have had to face reflected in these Challenge Card prompts? Consider customising the lower half of the Strategy Cards to your own context.

Synergies Explained...

During the Act, Synergise & Reflect stage, you may choose to play a **Synergy Card to earn bonus Strategy Strength**.

Some Strategy Cards have a **Synergy Symbol (&)** beside their Card Type Label. These are **Synergy Cards**. (See **Fig.8** which shows a Synergy Symbol along with a Strategy Strength of 3). Synergy Cards represent Strategies that become more powerful when used with other Strategies, reflecting your inherent ingenuity when you combine strategies in your own context for greater effect.

How to Score: Strategy Strength Bonuses

Synergy Cards can be played like any other Strategy Card, except that they can only be played onto an already played Strategy or Synergy Card, and **not directly onto a Challenge Card**. They earn bonus Strength when combined with other Strategies.

If you play a Synergy Card:

- Directly onto a Strategy Card → **earn bonus +1** **Strategy Strength**
- Directly onto another Synergy Card → **earn bonus +2**

Important Notes

- You may only play Synergy Cards from your Defence Tableau
- Bonus Strength is added immediately when the card is played
- Bonus Resilience Points should be recorded on your Resilience Tracker

Example 1

In round one, you play a 1 Strategy Card onto a Challenge Card.
In round two, you play a 2(&) Synergy Card onto that same card.

Because Synergy was played onto Strategy:

- Add bonus +1 Strategy Strength

Strategy Strength = 1 + (2 + 1 bonus) = Total 4 Strategy Strength

Example 2 (Fig.10)

In round one you play a 2 Strategy Card onto a Challenge Card.
In round two you play a 2(&) Synergy Card onto that same card. Because a Synergy Card was played onto a Strategy Card

- Add bonus +1 Strategy Strength

In round three, you play a 3(&) Synergy Card onto that same card. Because a Synergy Card was played onto a Synergy Card:

- Add bonus +2 Strategy Strength
- Add bonus +1 Resilience Points

Strategy Strength = 2 + (2 + 1 bonus) + (3 + 2 bonus) = 10 Strategy Strength

Stage 4: Rebalance

At the end of each round, follow these steps in this order:

Complete Challenges ≥

If the total Strategy Strength played onto a Challenge Card equals or exceeds the Challenge Strength* then the Challenge is completed. Gain Resilience Points equal to the Challenge Strength; record this on your Resilience Tracker. Excess Strategy Strength played on a Challenge Card is lost at this point. (*See note Pg.21)

Reveal a New Challenge

If any Challenges are still face down then turn one face up. If none remain, skip this step.

Replenish Your Defence Tableau

Refill your Defence Tableau back up to 5 cards by drawing from the Strategy Toolkit. Choose carefully based on the Challenges ahead.

- If there are not enough cards in the Strategy Toolkit, then refill the Strategy Toolkit from the Strategy Card Deck.
- If the Strategy Deck runs out, shuffle the Strategy Card Discard Pile and add the shuffled cards to the bottom of the Strategy Card Deck, then continue to deal into empty spaces in the Strategy Toolkit.
- If there are still not enough cards to refill the Defence Tableau from the Strategy Toolkit, and none of the cards in the Defence Tableau can reasonably be played, then Game End is triggered.

Optional: Refill the Toolkit

You may spend **-2 Resilience Points** to refill the Strategy Toolkit. If you choose to do so:

- Deal cards from the Strategy Deck into empty spaces in the Toolkit.
- If the Strategy Deck runs out, shuffle the Strategy Card Discard Pile and add the shuffled cards to the bottom of the Strategy Card Deck, then continue to deal into empty spaces in the Toolkit.
- If there are still not enough cards, refill the Toolkit as much as possible. This still costs **-2 Resilience Points**.

See **Fig.11** for an example of the game layout at the end of round three.

Discussion prompt: Are there challenges in your context that require you to spend precious resources on developing new strategies, whilst also continuing to focus on your core work and support your community?

End of Round Three, Step by Step Example (Fig.11)

1a. What Now!?! Draw an Event Card

1b. What Now!?! Event Effect example: rolling a value of three on the die, you count three places from the left of your Defence Tableau and remove the card you land on, then place it face up in the Strategy Discard Pile

1c. What Now!?! Strategy Discard Pile

2. Strategise! Discuss the Strategies available to you in your Defence Tableau, and those visible in the Strategy Toolkit for future rounds

3a. Act. Play one Strategy Card per visible Challenge Card at the Challenge Horizon

3b. Synergise. Playing a Synergy Card (&) earns bonuses

3c. Reflect. Name Actions relevant to your context to score Resilience

4a. Rebalance: Complete Challenges. Check for overcome Challenges and score them

4b. Rebalance: Reveal another Challenge by flipping an already dealt face down Challenge Card to a face up position at the Challenge Horizon

4c. Rebalance: Replenish your Defence Tableau from the Strategy Toolkit

4d. Rebalance: Optionally, refill the Strategy Toolkit

Check for Game End

The game ends when:

All dealt **Challenges are completed** OR
There are **no playable cards remaining** in the Defence Tableau and the Defence Tableau cannot be refilled

An individual Challenge has been overcome if the total Strategy Strength including bonuses played on a Challenge Card equals or exceeds the Strength of that Challenge Card.

An individual Challenge is complete when it is both overcome AND noted on your Resilience Tracker. You earn the value of the Challenge Card Strength* in Resilience Points.

There are no playable cards remaining if

- All Challenges have been flipped over and are visible, AND
- You decide there are no Strategies in the Defence Tableau that are relevant to the visible Challenges that remain to be dealt with at the Challenge Horizon, AND
- The Defence Tableau cannot be refilled, i.e.
 - The Defence Tableau has no spaces, OR
 - The Strategy Toolkit does not contain enough Cards to replenish the Defence Tableau, AND players cannot afford to/choose not to replenish the Strategy Toolkit from the Strategy Deck, or the Strategy Deck and Strategy Discard piles are empty.

Game End

An individual Challenge is complete when it is both overcome AND noted on your Resilience Tracker.

The game ends when:

- All dealt **Challenges are completed** OR
- There are **no playable cards remaining** in the Defence Tableau and the Defence Tableau cannot be refilled

"Ok, so I have all of these Resilience Points, but what do I do with them?"

Please turn to Pg.22 for Game End scoring and the Team Resilience Chart.

(*See note Pg.21)

How to Score: Resilience Points

In this section you can find all of the Resilience Point scoring rules in one place, for each step of the game, plus detailed steps of how to reflect scores on your Resilience Tracker.

RESIST/ANCE is a collaborative game, with no winners or losers, rather an opportunity to pause, and gather, to build Resilience in your team. This game does still have a scoring mechanism, however, using Resilience Points (RPs) to keep track of your team’s Resilience (score). You will use your Resilience Tracker to keep account of Resilience gained, lost and spent as the game progresses. You will find examples of Resilience Trackers which have been partially filled in, both in **Fig.13** in this section, and also in **Fig.23** at the end of the Resilience Tracker section.

You will start the game with 5 Resilience Points (**Fig.12**):

Resilience Points	Reason	Card Title	Action Identified	Takeaways/Reflections
+ 5	Starting points	n/a	Play RESIST/ANCE!	I thought the game was...

Resilience can then be earned during play; lost too; and spent, at the following points in the game:

At Setup

At the start of your game, your freshly printed Resilience Tracker will show that you have 5 Resilience Points to begin with, simply for taking the proactive step of sourcing this game and sitting down to play it! You can choose to use one Resilience Tracker for the team or you can have one per player so that each player can make personal notes.

During Stage 1: What Now!?

Unfortunately, Effects as a result of some Events can reduce your Resilience, but they sometimes increase it. Resilience Points can be gained or lost on each Event Card, one of which is revealed at the start of each round. Note your gain or loss on your Resilience Tracker as follows:

Resilience Points	Note +1 or -1 as directed on the Event Card Effect instructions, in the blue box on the lower half of the Event Card
Reason	“Event Card”
Card Title	The Event Card’s title, so you can refer back to this card if you wish
Action Identified	Note any Action that discussing this Event Card and resulting Effect may have inspired
Takeaways & Reflections	Note anything else about this Event and resulting Effect that you thought was important, interesting, or relevant to your context

During Stage 3: Synergise

Play a Synergy Card directly onto another Synergy Card → gain bonus +2 Strategy Strength and +1 **Resilience Point**. Note your gain on your Resilience Tracker as follows:

Resilience Points	Note +1
Reason	"Strategy Bonus"
Card Title	The Strategy Card titles, so that you can refer back to these cards if you wish
Action Identified	Note any Action that discussing synergising in this way may have prompted
Takeaways & Reflections	Note anything else about this Strategy Synergy that you think is important, interesting, or relevant to your context

During Stage 3: Reflect

Gain Resilience Points for naming Actions that could possibly be taken in the team's day to day lives, identified in response to both the Strategy Prompt(s) played onto a Challenge Card, and the prompt on the Challenge Card itself.

Name as many Actions as you can for each visible Challenge Card. One Resilience Point is earned per Action named. Note your brilliance on your Resilience Tracker as follows, filling in one line of the Tracker per Action identified:

Resilience Points	Note +1
Reason	"Strategy Action"
Card Title	The Relevant Strategy or Challenge Card title, so that you can refer back to the relevant card if you wish
Action Identified	Note the Action which was identified
Takeaways & Reflections	Note anything else about this Action that you think is important, interesting, or relevant to your context

During Stage 4: Rebalance - Complete Challenges Step →

You gain Resilience Points to the value of the Strength* of a Challenge Card once it is successfully overcome. Excess Strategy Strength is lost, an unfairness you may well be familiar with; it is the face value of the Challenge Card Strength* that you note on your Resilience Tracker. (*See note Pg. 21). **Complete** the Challenge by noting your achievement on your Resilience Tracker as follows:

Resilience Points	Note the Strength of the Challenge Card*, e.g. +7
Reason	"Challenge Overcome"
Card Title	The Challenge Card title, so that you can refer back to the relevant card if you wish
Action Identified	Note any Action that discussing this Challenge Card may have inspired
Takeaways & Reflections	Note anything else you thought was important or interesting about this Challenge, e.g. the Strategies used

*** N.B.:** Everyday challenges, and the Challenge Cards in the RESIST/ANCE game which represent them, are recognised to be of differing strengths and impacts in different contexts. In the base game however, all Challenge Cards are given a flat Strength of 7 so as not to prescribe a hierarchy of those Challenges. We encourage you to customise the Strength and Prompts on Challenge Cards, and indeed customise all cards, to more accurately reflect your own context and experiences.

Stage 4: Rebalance - Optional: Refill the Toolkit Step

You can optionally spend -2 Resilience Points to refill your Strategy Toolkit from the Strategy Card Deck at the end of each round. Remember to check your latest Resilience Points total by tallying the score on your Resilience Tracker. If you have enough Points to spend, and you decide to refill the strategy Toolkit, note your decision on your Resilience Tracker as follows:

Resilience Points	Note -2
Reason	"Refill Toolkit"
Card Title	n/a
Action Identified	Note any Action that this decision may have inspired
Takeaways & Reflections	Note anything you thought was important or interesting about your decision to spend Resilience in this instance

At Game End

At Game End, any Challenges which have not been overcome will cost you -1 Resilience Point each. Note this on your Resilience Tracker as follows:

Resilience Points	Note -1
Reason	"Remaining Challenge"
Card Title	n/a
Action Identified	n/a
Takeaways & Reflections	n/a

Resilience Tracker Example

At the end of Round One your Resilience Tracker might look something like this:

Resilience Points	Reason	Card Title	Action Identified	Takeaways/Reflections
+ 5	Starting points	n/a	Play RESIST/ANCE!	I thought the game was...
+ 1	Strategy bonus	Speaking up in daily life	in work l...	This made us feel... Contact the ...
+ 1	Strategy action	Set clear boundaries	when answering the phone...	Reach out to... Strategy template...
+ 1	Strategy action	Claiming public space	write to my local...	Review historical...
- 2	Refill toolkit	n/a	n/a	How do others monitor the challenge horizon safely and within their resource capabilities...

At Game End

An individual Challenge has been overcome if the total Strategy Strength including bonuses played on a Challenge Card equals or exceeds the Strength of that Challenge Card. You earn the value of the Challenge Card Strength* in Resilience Points .

An individual Challenge is complete when it is both overcome AND noted on your Resilience Tracker.

"Ok, so I have all of these Resilience Points, but what do I do with them?"

At Game End

- **Check** that you have scored all RPs during the game by referring to the 'How to Score: Resilience Points' section on Pg.19.
- **Complete** all overcome Challenges by **scoring** them on your Resilience Tracker. As noted above, you earn the value of the Challenge Card Strength* in Resilience Points .
- **Score -1** Resilience for each Challenge which remains undefeated at the Challenge Horizon.
- **Compare** and contrast your total collaboratively earned Resilience Points from this game to your total RP score from the last time you played. Discuss what was different this time, and what might have changed in your context since the last time you got together to play RESIST/ANCE.
- **Compare** the number of Challenges completed at game end to the following Team Resilience Chart (**Fig.14**). How did you do?:

Complete 2 Challenges = Resilience Masters

Complete 3 Challenges = Resource Guardians

Complete 4 Challenges = Solidarity Squad

Complete 5 Challenges = Mutual Aid Commanders

Complete 6 Challenges = Queerfeminist Rebels

Fig.14

*Discussion prompt: How did you do? What are your main takeaways from playing RESIST/ANCE this time? Why not compare the collaboratively earned RPs against your score from the last time you played, **discuss** what was different this time, and what might have changed in your context since the last time you played.*

Key Terms

Strategies

RESIST/ANCE Strategy Cards (Fig.15) provide Strategy Prompts derived from data found when studying the effects of 'anti-gender' politics on everyday lives with participants of the RESIST Project.

Strategies have a Strength , for which we have set initial random values; however, you can customise them so as to reflect their relative Strengths in your context. Increasing a Strategy's Strength would show that it is a Strategy that you find effective in your context, giving it greater impact on a Challenge; decreasing a Strategy's Strength would show that you find that Strategy less effective in your context. Simply cross out the initial Strength shown on the orange shield on the top left hand corner of your card and adjust the value to your context.

Synergies

Some Strategy Cards have a Synergy Symbol (&) beside their Card Type Label. These are called Synergy Cards .

A Synergy Card can be combined with another Strategy Card to unlock a **bonus Strategy Strength of +1** during the Stage 3: Act and Synergise Step.

Furthermore, a Synergy Card can be played onto an already played Synergy Card to earn both a **bonus Strategy Strength of +2 AND +2 Resilience Points**. You will find more detail, and examples, in the Synergies Explained section.

Strategy Toolkit

Your Strategy Toolkit (Fig.16) is the collection of Strategies you have honed over time. Deal the Strategy Toolkit from your shuffled deck of Strategy Cards at Setup in a 5x3 grid. Remember: you can add to your Strategy Deck by customising Wild Cards as Strategy Cards. **Strategy Toolkit**

Fig.16

Defence Tableau

Your Defence Tableau (**Fig.17**) is the selection of Strategies that are available for you to use when tackling a Challenge. Your Defence Tableau is dealt at the Setup stage from your shuffled deck of Strategy Cards in a row of five cards. Thereafter it is replenished from the Strategy Toolkit; it cannot be replenished directly from the Strategy Deck.

Play Strategies from your Defence Tableau onto Challenge Cards at the Challenge Horizon, with a goal of overcoming those Challenges. You cannot play Strategies directly from your Strategy Toolkit onto a Challenge Card; you must only play from your Defence Tableau.

Challenges

RESIST/ANCE Challenge Cards (**Fig.18**) provide prompts derived from data found when studying the effects of 'anti-gender' politics on everyday lives with participants of the RESIST Project. Challenge Cards also have a Strength* for which we have set an initial value of 7. We encourage you to customise these cards so as to make them relevant to the challenges you face in your context; simply cross out the initial Strength shown on the green shield the top left hand corner of the card and adjust it to your context. (*See note Pg.21)

Challenge Horizon

The Challenge Horizon (**Fig.19**) represents the daily Challenges that participants reported in our data. Your Challenge Horizon will have a selection of four Challenges, initially with two face up and two face down. You will play one Strategy Card onto each Challenge Card, per round, until you have overcome each Challenge, or have run out of Strategy Cards. You can choose to deal more or fewer Challenges as you wish to customise your game; see the 'Level Up!' Section on Pg.27.

Events & Effects

RESIST/ANCE Event Cards ⚡ (Fig.20) represent not just Events themselves, but crucially also represent the impact that 'anti-gender' mobilisation tactics have been shown to have in the RESIST Research. Such impacts are referred to as Effects ✨ in this game. Event Cards may be positive or negative, and have resulting positive or negative Effects. Some Event Cards ask you to use a die to carry out an Effect; if you don't have a die or a die app on your phone, you can have someone pick a random number between 1 and 6.

Wild Cards

RESIST/ANCE Wild Cards (Fig.21) are blank game cards that you can fill in with Strategies or Challenges from your context. A custom Strategy Card could, for example, be used to reflect wishful thinking. A custom Challenge Card could, for example, correspond to hard truths which have been experienced in your context.

Have a look at 'Customising the RESIST/ANCE Game' on Pg.26 for details of how to customise a Wild Card to add your own experiences right into the game.

Resilience Points (RPs)

Resilience Points are used to keep track of your team's Resilience (score). You will use your Resilience Tracker to keep account of Points gained and lost as the game progresses. You start with 5 Resilience Points, whilst more can be earned during play, lost too, and spent.

For a full list of stages in the game where Resilience Points can be gained, lost or spent; and how; and example Resilience Tracker Sheets, see the 'How to Score' section, Pg.19.

Resilience Tracker

Use a printed Resilience Tracker to keep track of Resilience Points gained, lost and spent over the course of the game. Check your final score against the last time you played, and see what Team Resilience Chart level your team has reached in this play of the game.

You will find a Resilience Tracker printable in the RESIST Zenodo RESIST/ANCE Game Resources download .zip. Follow this QR code to download it. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>

You can refer to partially filled in Resilience Tracker examples in **Figs.14 & 24**, which show example scores at the end of a first round.

Customising the RESIST/ANCE Game

You can play the game as it comes out of the pack; however, we encourage you, through reflecting on the prompts on the Strategy and Challenge Cards and discussing them in your group, to customise them for your own context and experiences as you play.

How to customise RESIST/ANCE

The prompts in this game are derived from research data found during the RESIST Research.

You can customise this game to your context in the following ways:

- **Customise the prompts** on Strategy by adding your own description in the space provided in the lower half of those cards
- **Change the Strength of the Strategy .** Increasing a Strategy's Strength would show that it is a Strategy that you find effective in your context, making it a stronger tactic against a Challenge; decreasing a Strategy's Strength would show that you find that Strategy less effective in your context. Simply cross out the initial Strength shown on the top left hand corner of your card and adjust it to your context.
- **Create your own cards.** You can further customise this game using the provided Wild Cards —the only limit is your imagination and time. To customise a Wild Card, use a pen to mark the card ✓ as your chosen Card Type on the back—either Strategy or Challenge—then cross out the (ir)relevant Card Type Label on the front of the card, and fill in the prompt field with your custom prompts.

You can download a Wild Card printable via this QR code... <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>

To custom make a...

...Strategy card

...Challenge card

Variants: Level Up!

If you would like to make this game more challenging, consider the following variants:

- **Customise the game.** By editing the existing cards and/or using the Wild Cards provided, you can weave your own thoughts, hopes, aspirations and experiences right into the RESIST/ANCE game. You can find instructions as to how to customise in the 'Customising the RESIST/ANCE Game' section of this document on Pg.26.

You can print extra Wild Cards using the free downloadable resource on the RESIST website, or via this QR Code...

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>

- **Increase the number of Challenge Cards dealt at game Setup.** The base game suggests you deal four Cards at Setup. However you could deal 5, 6, or more, meaning you can strive to increase your earned Resilience Points, and move up the Team Resilience Chart; but beware, you may run out of Strategy resources before you overcome all Challenges. Challenges which have not been overcome will cost you -1 Resilience at Game End!
- **Deal another Challenge Card at Stage 4: Rebalance - Reveal a New Challenge Card step.** If at the Reveal a New Challenge Card step you find that all Challenges have already been flipped over, deal a new Challenge Card face up at the Challenge Horizon. As with the previous variant, you may run out of Strategy resources before you overcome all Challenges. Challenges which have not been overcome will cost you -1 Resilience at Game End!
- **Increase the number of Challenge Cards that are initially dealt face down.** The base game suggests you deal two cards up at Setup. Perhaps you will only reveal one Challenge Card to begin with instead of two? This will make it more challenging to strategise, as you will not have sight of most of Challenges at the Challenge Horizon.
- **Locked Toolkit elements.** Deal a row, or multiple rows, of the Strategy Toolkit face down; these card values will remain hidden until unlocked when drawn at random during the Stage 4: Rebalance - Replenish Your Defence Tableau step. Any combination of visible or hidden Strategies can be selected from the Strategy Toolkit in this variation when bringing the Defence Tableau Card count back up to 5 cards.

Resilience Tracker

Choose whether to print one Resilience Tracker for your team, or one each for your personal takeaways and reflections.

The Resilience Tracker printable along with the full set of RESIST/ANCE resources are available in a handy .zip of RESIST/ANCE resources, available for download at the RESIST Zenodo Repository; scan the QR code here to jump to it. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>

Print a fresh copy of this and the next three pages, to include the Team Resilience Chart, from the Resilience Tracker printable, each time you play.

Resilience Points	Reason	Card Title	Action Identified	Takeaways/Reflections
+ 5	Starting points	n/a	Play RESIST/ANCE!	I thought the game was...

Resilience Points	Reason	Card Title	Action Identified	Takeaways/Reflections

Resilience Points	Reason	Card Title	Action Identified	Takeaways/Reflections

Total Resilience Points:

Team Resilience Chart

How many Challenges did you complete? Compare your team's results to this table and **celebrate!**

- Overcome 2 Challenges = Resilience Masters*
- Overcome 3 Challenges = Resource Guardians*
- Overcome 4 Challenges = Solidarity Squad*
- Overcome 5 Challenges = Mutual Aid Commanders*
- Overcome 6 Challenges = Queerfeminist Rebels*

Discussion prompt: How did you do? What are your main takeaways from playing RESIST/ANCE this time? Why not compare the collaboratively earned RPs against your score from the last time you played, **discuss** what was different this time, and what might have changed in your context since the last time you played.

Example Resilience Tracker Table:

Resilience Points	Reason	Card Title	Action Identified	Takeaways / Reflections
+ 5	Starting points	n/a	Play RESIST/ANCE!	I thought the game was...
+ 1	Strategy Action	"Legal Counselling"	Contact ...	It became clear that...
- 1	Event card	"Abandonment"	Write down the...	The process which...
+ 7	Challenge Overcome	"Legal Intimidation"	A pattern of...	It would be good to reach out to...
+ 1	Event Card	"Speaking Up to Push Back..."	Consider...	It can be so difficult to...
- 2	Toolkit refill	n/a	n/a	It was worth refilling because...
Total: 11RPs				

Fig. 23

Discussion Prompts Quick Reference

It is intended that this game might facilitate discussion and foster new understandings. To aid in this, you will have seen team discussion points in *italics* along the way, which hopefully prompted a deeper engagement with the content of the cards. Those moments were indicated by this Chat Icon.

Here is a quick reference of the discussion prompts which can be found throughout this booklet.

Stage 1: What Now!? Pg.13

Discussion prompt: What strategies have you depended on before that are no longer relevant in your context? What changed?

Stage 2: Strategise Pg.14

Discussion prompt: Consider customising the lower half of the Strategy Cards to your own context.

Stage 3: Act, Synergise & Reflect - Reflect Step Pg.14

Discussion prompt: Are any challenges you have had to face reflected in these Challenge Card prompts? Consider customising the lower half of the Strategy Cards to your own context.

Stage 4: Rebalance - Optional: Refill the Toolkit Step Pg.16

Discussion prompt: Are there challenges in your context that require you to spend precious resources on developing new strategies, whilst also continuing to focus on your core work and support your community?

Game End Pgs. 22 & 31

*Discussion prompt: How did you do? What are your main takeaways from playing RESIST/ANCE this time? Why not compare the collaboratively earned RPs against your score from the last time you played, **discuss** what was different this time, and what might have changed in your context since the last time you played.*

PUBLICATION INFORMATION

TITLE RESIST/ANCE: Strategies for a Better World. The RESIST Project's Card Game. Rules Document.

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DATE 2026

PUBLISHER RESIST Project

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18866120

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HOW TO CITE Grant, A. (2026). RESIST/ANCE: Strategies for a Better World. The RESIST Project's Card Game. Rules Document. RESIST Project.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18866120>

OUTPUT TYPE Other

OUTPUTS REPOSITORY <https://zenodo.org/communities/resistproject/>

PROJECT WEBSITE <https://theresistproject.eu/>

FUNDING Funded by the European Union under Project ID 101060749. EU Horizon Europe (EU partners); UK Government Horizon Europe Guarantee Scheme (UK partner); Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (Swiss partners).

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or British and Swiss funding authorities. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

RESIST/ANCE—Strategies for a Better World

Based on the RESIST Research Project: www.theresistproject.eu

An output of the RESIST Research project, ID:101060749

**Funded by
the European Union**